

ADVANCES IN REQUIREMENTS ENGINEERING FOR WELL-BEING, AGING, AND HEALTH

This briefing reports scientific evidence on advances in requirements engineering for well-being, aging, and health.

To obtain the findings, we conducted a systematic mapping study considering the following premier venues of Requirements Engineering:

- International Working Conference on Requirement Engineering: Foundation for Software Quality (REFSQ).
- IEEE International Requirements Engineering conference (RE).
- International Workshop on Requirements Engineering for Well-Being, Aging, and Health (REWBAH).
- Requirements Engineering Journal (REJ).

FINDINGS

We found evidence that all requirements engineering activities have been used to develop well-being, aging, and health applications, but requirements elicitation has been the most used to date.

The main research topics investigated are:

- **Healthcare and Telemedicine:** it has primary focus on systems used for healthcare, as well as mobile applications dedicated to supporting patients and their treatments.
- **Intelligent Technology:** it introduces elements of machine learning, the Internet of Things, and intelligent assistants for health, wellness, and aging.
- **Human Interaction and Medical Communication:** it focuses on human interactions and the health of healthcare professionals, and individuals in other fields.
- **Mental and Emotional Health:** it focuses on mental and emotional aspects.
- **Inclusion and Accessibility:** it addresses accessible and inclusive software and systems for various situations, such as the elderly or people with disabilities.
- **Patient Support and Follow-up:** it presents solutions and focuses on clinical follow-up of patients.

The most frequently addressed research topic has been Healthcare & Telemedicine, particularly in

the stages of Requirements Elicitation and Requirements Analysis.

The most common research type is Solution Proposal, but more studies are needed in the Philosophical and Opinion Paper categories.

Most of the solutions for WBAH have been evaluated by case studies.

The Solution Proposal research type is by far the most related to topics. It strongly focuses on all topics, especially Healthcare & Telemedicine, Inclusion & Accessibility, and Intelligent Technology. They are followed by Validation Research and Evaluation Research, which also have a significant presence.

The primary research opportunities are:

- **Security and privacy:** Future research may investigate the continuous integration of security and privacy considerations throughout the software life cycle, from requirements elicitation to implementation and evaluation.
- **Machine learning and data-driven approaches:** This research opportunity delves into the potential for innovation in requirements engineering by examining various strategies to optimize and adapt processes. Specifically, it focuses on integrating machine learning techniques into the day-to-day operations of WBAH systems to improve efficiency and decision-making processes.
- **User experience, usability, and evaluation:** There are opportunities to improve the user experience in healthcare systems, with a focus on patients and healthcare professionals. These research opportunities will pave the way for improving human-technology interaction, contributing to more effective systems that meet users' emotional and functional needs.
- **Elicitation and modeling techniques:** Research on elicitation and modeling techniques opens up several possibilities in health and technology. It is possible to explore design patterns for the development of applications aimed at older adults, and there is also room for research focused on medical decision support systems.
- **Ethical and human-centric considerations:** The articles in this category show how future research should explore ethical and human values that are practically embedded in software design processes and emerging technologies.
- **Technology for older adults:** These studies suggest that future research can explore ways to make technology more accessible and motivating for older adults

while respecting their limitations and psychological barriers.

- **Requirements engineering for mobile applications:** Research in mobile applications, particularly in health monitoring, can improve requirements engineering in WBAH systems. For instance, developing tools that integrate user feedback into the requirements engineering process can lead to more accurate adaptation to user needs.

Who is this briefing for?

Software engineering practitioners who want to make decisions about how to develop well-being, aging, and health applications.

Where the findings come from?

All findings of this briefing were extracted from the mapping study conducted by **Omitted due to double blind review**.

What is included in this briefing?

The main findings of the original systematic mapping review, and brief contextual information about the context of the findings

What is not included in this briefing?

Additional information not supported by the findings of the original systematic mapping review as well as descriptions about the research method or details about the primary studies analyzed in the original systematic mapping review.

For additional information about our research groups:

- **Systems and Software Engineering Laboratory (Labs²):**
<https://sites.google.com/view/labs2/home>
- **Technical Debt Research Team:**
<https://www.tdresearchteam.com/home>